

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

Treatment Preferences in Patients with Hypothyroidism: An Analysis of Eleven Randomized Controlled Trials

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Supplemental Table 1: Study and participant characteristics in the included randomized controlled trials:

Autor, year, country.	Number of patients, Follow-up time (weeks)	Dose of L-T3	Outcomes of the study	Patient preference for treatment	Main results
Study design	Sex fem (n, %), age (years, SD or IQR), comorbidities	Etiology of hypothyroidism	Evaluated questionnaires	Minimum sample size (n); power (%); variables assessed	Limitations
Appelhof et al 2005 (1), Netherlands	140, 15 weeks	L-T4/L-T3 10:1 2x L-T4/L-T3 5:1 2x	Patient medication preference (at study conclusion); scales for assessing cognition, mood, symptoms, and QOL.	L-T4: 14/48 (29%) L-T4+L-T3 (10:1): 19/46 (41%) L-T4+L-T3 (5:1) 24/46 (52%) P = 0.024	The primary outcome, patient preference for treatment, favored L-T4/L-T3. Significant weight loss was observed in patients receiving L-T4:L-T3 5:1.
Double-blind, randomized, parallel study	120 (85.1), 48.5 (9.4), comorbidities not assessed.	Primary autoimmune hypothyroidism	RBMT, CVLT, MCT, POMS, MFI-20, RAND-36, and SCL-90.	Data not available in the article.	The study was not a crossover design. Did not assess associated comorbidities.
Brigante et al 2023 (2), Italy	121 24 weeks	L-T4/L-T3 20:1 ± 2.5 µg (drops) 2x	Changes in serum SHBG levels; scales for assessing QOL and symptoms, based on genetic variants DIO2-rs225014 and MCT10-rs17606253.	L-T4: 7/63 (11%) L-T4+L-T3 (20:1): 7/58 (12%) P = 0.086	L-T4+L-T3 therapy, adjusted by TSH levels and including twice-daily L-T3, restores the physiological ft3/ft4 ratio. The study showed no impact on peripheral tissue markers, quality of life, or clinical parameters. Neither preference nor therapeutic compensation is influenced by DIO2-rs225014 and MCT10-rs17606253.
Double-blind, randomized, parallel study	100 (71.4), 56 (12), Hypertension, DM, hyperlipidemia, hypoparathyroidism and other comorbidities	Totally thyroidectomized for benign or malignant disease	ThyPRO scores; Morisky Medication Adherence Scale, SHBG, osteocalcin, CTX, and bone isoenzyme of alkaline phosphatase	113; 90%; Important for accurately assessing serum SHBG variations.	The study was not a crossover design.
Bunevicius et al 1999 (3), Lithuania	33, 5 weeks	01 Capsule (12.5 µg) per day	Scales for assessing cognition, depression, cardiovascular, and peripheral nervous system.	L-T4: 2/33 (6%) L-T4+L-T3: 20/33 (60.6%)	L-T4+L-T3 therapy improved cognitive performance and mood in hypothyroid patients, with 6 out of 17 cognitive tests and 10 out of 15 mood assessments showing better results. While

				No preference: 11/33 (33.4%) (P=0.017)	pulse rate and serum sex hormone-binding globulin concentrations increased slightly, other parameters remained similar.
Double-blind, randomized, controlled trial	31 (94), 46 (13), comorbidities not assessed.	Hypothyroidism (autoimmune and thyroid cancer treated by near-total thyroidectomy)	Digit Symbol Test, Digit Span Test of the WAIS, VST, BDI, POMS, and HRSD.	Data not available in the article.	The number of patients was significantly reduced. Fixed and once-daily dose (12.5 µg) for all patients.
Bunevicius et al 2002 (4), Lithuania	10, 5 weeks	01 Capsule (10 µg) per day	Scales for assessing cognition, depression, cardiovascular, and body composition changes.	L-T4: 2/10 (20%) L-T4+L-T3: 6/10 (60%) No preference: 2/10 (20%) P=0.0907	Combined hormone replacement led to improvements in mental state, reflected in specific mood scales, but without notable enhancements in cognitive tests. Also, alterations in left ventricular diastolic function were seen, with no significant changes in body composition after the combined treatment.
Double-blind, randomized, crossover study	10;10 (100), 34 (19-58), comorbidities not assessed.	Hypothyroidism after thyroidectomy for Graves's disease	Digit Symbol Test, Digit Span Test of the WAIS, POMS, BDI, and VAS	Data not available in the article.	The number of patients was significantly reduced. Fixed and once-daily dose (10 µg) for all patients.
Escobar-Morreale et al 2005 (5), Spain	26 (14/12), 8 weeks	01 Capsule (5 µg ou 7.5 µg) per day	Changes in serum thyroid hormone levels; scales for assessing cognition, mood, and QOL.	L-T4: 18/26 (69.2%) L-T4+L-T3: 2/26 (7.7%) No preference: 6/26 (23%)	The treatment with L-thyroxine-liothyronine combinations, which replicate the ratio of thyroxine to triiodothyronine in human thyroid secretion, does not offer any objective advantage over treatment with L-thyroxine alone, although patients prefer combination therapy.
Double-blind, randomized, crossover study	26/26 (100), 48 (11), comorbidities not assessed.	Chronic lymphocytic thyroiditis and thyroid ablation for Graves' disease or toxic multinodular goiter	Digit Symbol Substitution Test, Digit Span Test, VST, POMS, and Echocardiography	N/A; 80%; Attained power for detecting treatment effects on fatigue, depression, anger-hostility, and cognitive performance.	The number of patients was significantly reduced. Fixed and once-daily dose (5 or 7.5 µg) for all patients.
Fadeyev et al. 2010 (6), Russia	36 women T4: 20 T4/T3: 16 24 weeks	01 Capsule (12.5 µg) per day	Changes in serum thyroid hormone levels, lipid levels, ECG monitoring, bone densitometry, osteocalcin levels, and thyroid symptoms	L-T4: 8/36 (22.2%) L-T4+L-T3: 10/36 (27.8%) No preference: 18/36 (50%)	No significant difference between monotherapy and combined therapy was observed in TSH levels, ECG monitoring, densitometry, or thyroid symptom scores. In the L-T4 + L-T3 group, total cholesterol and LDL decreased by 50% (p < 0.05), while no difference was found in serum osteocalcin levels between treatments.
Double-blind, randomized, parallel study	36/36 (100%), 41.5 (33-45),	Primary hypothyroidism	Osteocalcin, 24-hour ECG monitoring and lipoprotein profiles	Data not available in the article.	The study was not a crossover design. The number of patients was significantly reduced and only women.

	exclusion criteria included major comorbidities.	(without specifying the cause).			Fixed and once-daily dose (12.5 µg) for all patients.
Hoang et al 2013 (7), USA	70, 16 weeks	1 mg DTE = 1.667µ L-T4 and 0.39µ L-T3 the dose of DTE during the study was 80.63 (29.97) mg/d (±31.4 µ/d L-T3)	Scales for assessing cognition, depression, symptoms, and quality of life (QOL).	L-T4: 13/70 (18.5%) DTE: 34/70 (48.5%) No preference: 23/70 (33%)	This preliminary study suggests that substituting once-daily DTE for L-T4 in thyroid hormone therapy may lead to slight weight loss and potential enhancements in symptoms and mental well-being, with minimal adverse effects.
Double-blind, randomized, crossover study	53 (75.7%), 50.6 (23-65), comorbidities not assessed.	Primary hypothyroidism (autoimmune, surgery and radioiodine)	TSQ-36, GHQ-12, WMS-IV, and BDI	67, 80%, Achieved power to discern treatment differences in TSQ scores.	Did not evaluate combination therapy using L-T4 and L-T3.
Nygaard et al 2009 (8), Denmark	59, 12 weeks	01 tablet (20 µg) per day	Scales for assessing depression, and quality of life (QOL); Changes in bioimpedance and waist-to-hip ratio.	L-T4: 9/59 (15.3%) L-T4+L-T3: 29/59 (49.1%) No preference: 21/59 (35.6%)	The combination therapy (L-T3 20 mg once daily) outperformed monotherapy, showing superiority in various QOL, depression, and anxiety rating scales, along with patient preference.
Double-blind, randomized, crossover study	55 (93.2%), 46 (12.5), comorbidities not assessed.	Primary autoimmune hypothyroidism	SF-36, BDI, SCL 90-R, bioimpedance, and waist-to-hip ratio	56, 80%, Detected meaningful differences in SF-36 parameters.	Fixed and once-daily dose (20 µg) for all patients.
Rodriguez et al 2005 (9), USA	27, 6 weeks	01 Capsule (10 µg) per day	Scales for assessing symptoms, cognition, depression, and QOL. Changes in serum thyroid hormone levels, heart rate, blood pressure, and weight.	L-T4: 7/27 (26%) L-T4+L-T3: 12/27 (44.4%) No preference: 8/27 (29.6%)	Substitution of L-T3 at a 1:5 ratio for a portion of baseline L-T4 was no better than treatment with the original dose of L-T4 alone. There were no significant differences in fatigue and symptoms of depression between treatments.
Double-blind, randomized, crossover study	25 (83%), 47.5 (12.9), comorbidities not assessed.	Primary hypothyroidism (autoimmune, surgery and radioiodine)	PFS, WMS-III, VAS, BDI-II, and GHQ-30	Sample size was not predetermined. Post-study power analysis: detected treatment effects with >99% power for fatigue assessment.	The number of patients was significantly reduced. Fixed and once-daily dose (10 µg) for all patients.
Shakir et al 2021 (10), USA	75, 22 weeks	01 Capsule 1:10 (10 µg) per day 1 mg DTE = 1.667µ L-T4 and 0.39µ L-T3 the dose of DTE during the study was	Primary outcome: measures included performance in the (1) WMS-IV, (2) BDI, or (3) TSQ and (4) GHQ-12. Secondary outcome: (1) thyroid function tests, (2) body weight and lipid profile, (3) treatment preference, (4) etiology of	L-T4: 15/75 (20%) DTE: 29/75 (38.6%) L-T4 + L-T3: 23/75 (30.7%) No preference: 8/75 (10.7%)	No differences were observed in the TSQ-36 and GHQ12 questionnaires, or in the BDI and the 5 subdomains of WMS-IV test assessments. Treatment preference was not different and there were no interferences of the etiology of

		80.63 (29.97) mg/d (±31.4 µ/d L-T3)	hypothyroidism, and (5) Thr92Ala-DIO2 gene polymorphism.		hypothyroidism or Thr92Ala-DIO2 gene polymorphism in the outcomes.
Double-blind, randomized, crossover study	58 (77.3%), 50 (29-65), comorbidities not assessed.	Hypothyroidism (autoimmune, surgery, radioiodine and idiopathic)	TSQ-36, GHQ-12, VMS-IV, and BDI	67, 80%, Ensured detection of differences in TSQ-36 scores between treatments.	The number of patients was significantly reduced for a crossover study involving three distinct groups, with each arm ending up with fewer than 13 patients.
Walsh et al 2003 (11), Australia	101 10 weeks	01 Capsule (10 µg) per day	Patient medication preference (at study conclusion); scales for assessing QOL, cognition, symptoms, and QOL.	L-T4: 46/101 (46%) L-T4+L-T3: 36/101 (36%) No preference: 18/101 (18%)	No evidence supported improved well-being, cognitive function, quality of life, or increased thyroid hormone action on peripheral tissues with combined L-T4/L-T3 replacement, as compared to L-T4 alone in this study's dosage regimen.
Double-blind, randomized, crossover study	94 (92%), 47.7 (11.7), hypertension, depression, hyperlipidemia and other comorbidities.	Hypothyroidism (autoimmune, surgery and radioiodine)	SF-36, GHQ-28, TSQ, Zulewski score, VAS, SDMT, and DST	100, 80-90%, Detected significant differences in SF-36, GHQ-28, TSQ, SDMT, and DST.	Fixed and once-daily dose (10 µg) for all patients.

BDI - Beck Depression Inventory; **CI** - Confidence Interval; **CTX** - Carboxy-terminal collagen cross-links; **CVLT** - California Verbal Learning Test; **DM** - Diabetes Mellitus; **DTE** - Desiccated Thyroid Extract; **DST** - Digit Span Test; **ECG** - Electrocardiogram; **GHQ-12** - General Health Questionnaire 12; **GHQ-30** - General Health Questionnaire-30; **HRSD** - Hamilton Rating Scale for Depression; **IQR** - Interquartile Range; **L-T3** - Liothyronine; **L-T4** - Levothyroxine; **MCT** - Memory Comparison Task; **MFI-20** - Multidimensional Fatigue Inventory; **NMA** - Network Meta-Analysis; **PFS** - Piper Fatigue Scale; **POMS** - Profile of Mood States; **QOL** - Quality of Life; **RAND-36** - 36-Item Short Form Survey; **RBMT** - Rivermead Behavioral Memory Test; **RCT** - Randomized Controlled Trial; **RR** - Relative Risk; **SCL 90-R** - Symptom Checklist 90-Revised; **SCL-90** - Symptom Checklist-90; **SD** - Standard Deviation; **SDMT** - Symbol Digit Modalities Test; **SF-36** - Short Form Health Survey 36; **SHBG** - Sex Hormone Binding Globulin; **ThyPRO** - Thyroid Patient-Reported Outcome; **TSQ-36** - Thyroid Symptom Questionnaire 36; **VAS** - visual analogue scaling; **VMS-IV** - Wechsler Memory Scale, Fourth Edition; **VST** - Visual Scanning Test, **WAIS** - Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale.

Supplemental Figure 1 - Forest plot of patient preferences across crossover trials in patients with a TSH difference ($<0.1 \mu\text{UI/mL}$) between combined therapy and monotherapy:

Supplemental Figure 2 - Forest plot of patient preferences across crossover trials in patients with a TSH difference ($>0.1 \mu\text{UI/mL}$) between combined therapy and monotherapy:

Supplemental Figure 3 - Forest plot of patient preferences (combined therapy vs monotherapy) across parallel trials:

Supplemental Figure 4 – Power analysis of patient preferences (combined therapy vs monotherapy) following the exclusion of four studies (Bunevicius et al., 1999; Walsh et al., 2003; Escobar et al., 2005; Shakir et al., 2021), after funnel plot analysis:

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Supplemental Figure 12 - Meta-regression bubble plots exploring potential associations between difference TSH ($\mu\text{UI}/\text{mL}$) and treatment preference in combined therapy: A. Across all 11 selected studies and B. Across crossover trials (8 studies).

Supplemental Table 2: Assessment of inconsistency based on separate indirect from direct evidence using back-calculation method and random effects model.

Study Models	Comparison	Number of studies	Proportion	NMA	Direct effect (RR)	Indirect effect (RR)	RoR	Z-value	P-value
All included studies	L-T4: DTE	2	0.86	0.43	0.45	0.34	1.32	0.25	0.8042
	L-T4+L-T3: DTE	1	0.51	0.81	0.79	0.83	0.96	-0.05	0.9587
	L-T4: L-T4+L-T3	10	0.98	0.53	0.53	0.37	1.44	0.24	0.8103
Only crossover studies	L-T4: DTE	2	0.87	0.40	0.44	0.19	2.40	0.61	0.5438
	L-T4+L-T3: DTE	1	0.53	0.96	0.79	1.18	0.67	-0.38	0.7010
	L-T4: L-T4+L-T3	7	0.97	0.41	0.42	0.37	1.14	0.07	0.9444

L-T3 - Liothyronine; L-T4 - Levothyroxine; NMA - Estimated treatment effect (RR) in network meta-analysis; RR - Risk Relative; RoR - Ratio of Ratios (direct versus indirect).

Supplemental Table 3: Characteristics of the main meta-analyses published on the subject:

Autor, year, places	Number of initial citations in PRISMA	Outcome measure	Preference patients – [RR (CI), heterogeneity I² (%), p-value]	Conclusion
Study designs evaluated	Number of studies, (number patients)	Assessing risk of bias in included studies? (methodology); number of high-risk studies and studies of some concerns.	Funnel plot, Metaregression, Network meta-analyses	Limitations
Amit Akirov et al 2019 (12) Israel and USA	4192	Patient medication preference.	Combined therapy: 0.46 (CI 0.40–0.52; I ² = 18%), p = 0.231 Does not present data on the other preferences.	In randomized controlled trials with blinded treatment allocation, approximately half of the participants preferred combined L-T3 and L-T4 therapy over L-T4 alone; however, this difference was not statistically significant.
RCTs (parallel or crossover)	7 studies 348 patients	Yes (Cochrane’s RoB 2.0); one high-risk and five some concerns	Funnel plot and Network meta-analyses were not evaluated. Meta-regression: Total daily L-T3 dosage (ug) on combination therapy; Ratio of L-T3 divided by L-T4 dosage (ug) on combination therapy.	A reduced number of studies and no funnel plot was conducted. Individuals who preferred L-T4 or had no treatment preference were considered as not preferring combination therapy. Consequently, there was an underestimation of the combined therapy group, which could have had a statistical impact on the results.
Beltrao et al 2024 Brazil and USA	19385	Patient medication preference.	Combined therapy vs L-T4 mono: 2.84 (CI 1.50–5.39; I ² = 86%, p= 0.001); Combined therapy vs no preference: 2.09 ([CI 1.47–2.98]; I ² = 65%, p<0.0001)	Patients with hypothyroidism show a strong preference for combination therapy (L-T3+L-T4 or DTE) over L-T4 monotherapy. The reduction of heterogeneity by excluding outlier studies strengthens these results, with crossover study analyses reaffirming the preference for combination therapy, showing an RR of 2.84 (95% CI: 1.50 to 5.39; p < 0.00001).
RCTs (parallel or crossover)	11 studies 592 patients	Yes (Cochrane’s RoB 2.0); one high-risk and six some concerns	Funnel plot and Network meta-analyses were evaluated. Meta-regression: the daily dose of L-T3 (µg), duration of follow-up (weeks), and age (years).	The limitations include a small sample size and reduced number of studies, limited direct evidence in NMAs, and a lack of consideration for ethnic and genetic diversity, similar to other meta-analyses.
Lan et al 2022 (13),	2029	Scales for symptoms (fatigue, pain, anxiety, and anger), depression, adverse events	Combined therapy vs monotherapy: 2.47 (CI 1.31-4.67; I ² = 86%).	No significant difference in efficacy was found between combination and monotherapy across

China		improvement, and quality of life. Other outcomes: Patient medication preference, serum thyroid hormone levels, lipids metabolism, weight, echocardiographic parameters.	$p < 0.01$	various symptoms (bodily pain, depression, anxiety, and fatigue), QOL, body weight, and lipoprotein profiles.
(RCTs (parallel or crossover) and quasiexperimental studies)	18 studies 1216 patients	Yes (Cochrane's RoB 1.0); eighty high-risk and nine some concerns	The funnel plot was evaluated solely to analyze the depression and anxiety variables between the groups. Meta-regression was not evaluated.	Non-randomized studies were included (quasiexperimental studies), and meta-regression was not conducted.
Millan-Alanis et al 2021 (14), Mexico and USA	1399	Patient medication preference; scales for assessing clinical status, symptoms (fatigue), psychological distress, depression, adverse events improvement, and QOL. Other outcomes: scales for assessing anxiety symptoms, insomnia, somatic symptoms, cognitive, social dysfunction, all-cause mortality, and proportion of participants achieving suppressed TSH.	Combined therapy: 0.43 (CI 0.34–0.52; $I^2 = 48\%$). Monotherapy: 0.23 ([CI 0.14–0.35]; $I^2 = 77\%$). No preference: 0.30 ([CI 0.21–0.41]; $I^2 = 66\%$) $p < 0.01$	Low-to-moderate certainty evidence finds no difference in outcomes between L-T4/L-T3 and L-T4 alone, except patient preference. Adverse events seem similar, but only narratively observed.
RCTs (parallel or crossover) and quasiexperimental studies	11 studies 829 patients	Yes (Cochrane's RoB 2.0 and ROBINS-I); three high-risk and five some concerns	Funnel plot and meta-regression were not evaluated.	Non-randomized studies were included (quasiexperimental studies) and meta-regression was not conducted.

CI - Confidence Interval; **DTE** - Desiccated Thyroid Extract; **I^2** - Heterogeneity Index; **L-T3** - Liothyronine; **L-T4** - Levothyroxine; **NMA** - Network Meta-Analysis; **QOL** - Quality of Life; **RCT** - Randomized Controlled Trial; **ROBINS-I** - Risk of Bias In Non-randomized Studies of Interventions; **RR** - Relative Risk; **RoB 1.0** - Cochrane's Risk of Bias 1.0 tool; **RoB 2.0** - Cochrane's Risk of Bias 2.0 tool; **TSH** - Thyroid Stimulating Hormone; **USA** - United States of America.

Supplemental Table 4: Study and participant characteristics in the excluded randomized controlled trials:

Autor, year, country.	Number of patients, Follow-up time (weeks)	Dose of L-T3	Outcomes of the study	Patient preference for treatment	Main results
Study design	Sex fem (n, %), age (years, SD or IQR)	Etiology of hypothyroidism	Evaluated questionnaires	Reason for exclusion from our meta-analysis:	Limitations
Bjerkreim et al, 2022 (15), Norway	59, 24 weeks	L-T4/L-T3 3:1 1x	Quality of life assessed by three different questionnaires (ThyPRO, SF-36, Fatigue Questionnaire), thyroid function tests, cardiovascular parameters	28 (60%) preferred L-T3, 16 (34%) preferred L-T4, 3 (6%) had no preference	L-T3 treatment significantly improved quality of life, especially in terms of less tiredness and cognitive complaints compared to L-T4. No significant differences in cardiovascular effects were observed.
Non-blinded, randomized, crossover study	59 (100%), 42.9 (9.7), exclusion criteria included major comorbidities.	Primary hypothyroidism (autoimmune, surgery and radioiodine)	ThyPRO, SF-36, Fatigue Questionnaire	Non-blinded study design	The study was non-blinded, which may have led to biased results. The number of patients was significantly reduced and only women.
Clyde et al 2003 (16), USA	46, 16 weeks	01 Capsule (7.5 µg) twice daily	Scores on a hypothyroid-specific health-related quality-of-life (HRQL) questionnaire, body weight, serum lipid levels, and 13 neuropsychological	Data not available in the article.	No significant beneficial changes in body weight, serum lipid levels, hypothyroid symptoms as measured by the HRQL questionnaire, and standard neuropsychological tests.
Double-blind, randomized, parallel study	19 (86%), 43.1 (11.3), comorbidities not assessed.	Primary autoimmune hypothyroidism	HRQL questionnaire, 13 neuropsychological tests	No preference outcome data	The study was not a crossover design. Small sample size, short duration, possible placebo effect, not a crossover design
Kaminski et al, 2016 (17), Brazil	32, 16 weeks	01 Capsule (15 µg) per day	Thyroid function tests, lipid profile, plasma glucose, body weight, electrocardiogram, vital signs, and quality of life (QoL)	Data not available in the article.	Combination therapy led to significantly lower free T4 levels, with no changes in TSH or T3 levels. More patients on L-T4/L-T3 had elevated T3 levels, but no significant alterations in evaluated outcomes.
Double-blind, randomized, crossover study	30 (94%), 42.6 (13.3), exclusion criteria included major comorbidities.	Primary hypothyroidism (autoimmune, surgery and radioiodine)	HRQOL questionnaire, VAS for well-being, interest in sex, and ability to engage in physical activities, social interactions, and work	No preference outcome data	Small sample size and the absence of an assessment of patient treatment preferences.

Sawka et al 2003 (18), Canada	40, 15 weeks	01 Capsule (12.5 µg) twice daily	SCL-90, CES-D, and the Medical Outcomes Study.	Data not available in the article.	The combination of L-T4 and L-T3 did not show significant benefits over L-T4 alone in improving depressive symptoms, mood, or general well-being
Double-blind, randomized, controlled trial	36 (90%), 47.3 (11.0), exclusion criteria included major comorbidities.	Primary autoimmune hypothyroidism	SCL-90, CES-D, MOS, health status questionnaire	No preferred outcome data	Small sample size, high dropout rate, lack of objective psychiatric assessment, and the absence of an assessment of patient treatment preferences.
Smith et al 1970 (19), UK	87, 16 weeks	L-T4/L-T3 4:1 1x	Preference for treatment, serum protein-bound iodine levels, T3-resin sponge uptake values, incidence of unpleasant symptoms	42 (48%) no preference, 29 (33%) preferred L-T4 alone, 16 (18%) preferred the combination	The combination of L-T4 and L-T3 was not superior to L-T4 alone in improving well-being. There was a high incidence of unpleasant symptoms with the combination therapy.
Double-blind, randomized, crossover study	74 (85%), 55 (46-63), comorbidities not assessed.	Primary hypothyroidism (autoimmune, surgery and radioiodine)	Questionnaire assessing preference for treatment, side effects, and intercurrent illnesses	The high rate of medication non-adherence, with only 27% of patients taking the medication correctly, resulted in unreliable outcomes.	Potential bias in patient preference due to side effects from the high T3 dose (highest among the studies), high non-adherence rate, and 56% of patients developed hyperthyroidism symptoms.
Krysiak et al, 2018 (20), Poland	20, 24 weeks	L-T4/L-T3 5:1 1x	Affects sexual functioning and depressive symptoms in young men	Data not available in the article.	L-T4/L-T3 combination therapy improved sexual desire but did not significantly affect other aspects of sexual functioning or depressive symptoms compared to L-T4 alone
Single-blind, quasi-randomized, parallel study	21 males (100%), 35.5 (5.5), exclusion criteria included major comorbidities.	Primary hypothyroidism	IIEF-15, BDI-II	No preferred outcome data; quasi-randomized study (single-blind).	The number of patients was significantly reduced and only men. Subjective self-report questionnaires and the absence of an assessment of patient treatment preferences.
Krysiak et al, 2018 (21), Poland	37, 24 weeks	L-T4/L-T3 5:1 1x	To assess sexual functioning, as well as the presence and severity of depressive symptoms in young women.	Data not available in the article.	Combination therapy was superior to L-T4 alone in improving sexual desire and arousal, with a trend towards improvement in total FSFI score and reduction in BDI-II score
Single-blind, quasi-randomized, parallel study	37 females (100%), 30.5 (6), comorbidities not assessed.	Hypothyroidism induced by partial thyroidectomy	FSFI, BDI-II	No preferred outcome data; quasi-randomized study (single-blind).	The number of patients was significantly reduced and only women. Subjective self-report questionnaires and the absence of an assessment of patient treatment preferences.
Siegmund et al, 2004 (22), Germany	26, 12 weeks	L-T4/L-T3 14:1 1x	Mood states and cognitive performance measured by standardized psychological tests, serum TSH, free T3 (fT3), free T4 (fT4)	Data not available in the article.	The combination of L-T4 and L-T3 did not improve well-being or cognitive performance compared to L-T4 alone. There was a higher risk of signs of subclinical hyperthyroidism with the combination therapy.

Double-blind, randomized, crossover study	21 (80.7%), 46 (23-69), comorbidities not assessed.	Primary hypothyroidism (autoimmune, surgery and radioiodine)	BDI, STAI, SCL-90, FAW, POMS, Semantic Differential, Digit Span Test, Digit Symbol Test, VST	No preferred outcome data	Small sample size, lack of significant differences in mood and cognitive performance despite higher serum T3 levels with combination therapy and the absence of an assessment of patient treatment preferences.
Valizadeh et al, 2009 (23), Iran	60, 16 weeks	01 Capsule (6.25 µg) twice daily	Psychosocial issues (assessed by GHQ-28) and changes in body weight, heart rate, blood pressure, and serum lipid levels.	Data not available in the article.	No significant improvement in psychosocial outcomes, body weight, heart rate, blood pressure, or serum lipid levels with combined therapy compared to L-T4 alone, except for a reduction in anxiety/insomnia in the combined group
Double-blind, randomized, parallel study	48 (80%), 39 (11.4), exclusion criteria included major comorbidities.	Primary hypothyroidism (autoimmune, surgery and radioiodine)	GHQ-28	No preference outcome data	Limitations include a small sample size, reliance on self-reported questionnaires for psychosocial status, and the absence of an assessment of patient treatment preferences.

BDI - Beck Depression Inventory; **BDI-II** - Beck Depression Inventory-Second Edition; **CES-D** - Comprehensive Epidemiological Screens for Depression; **FAW** - Physical Well-being Questionnaire; **FSFI** - Female Sexual Function Index; **GHQ-28** - Goldberg's General Health Questionnaire; **HRQL** - Hypothyroid-specific Health-Related Quality of Life questionnaire; **IIEF-15** - International Index of Erectile Function-15; **MOS** - Medical Outcomes Study health status questionnaire; **POMS** - Profile of Mood States; **SCL-90** - Symptom Check-List-90; **SF-36** - Short Form (36) Health Survey; **STAI** - Spielberger State-Trait Anxiety Inventory; **ThyPRO** - Thyroid Patient-Reported Outcome; **VAS** - Visual Analog Scale; **VST** - Visual Scanning Test.

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